

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D1.3 Project website

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ACRONYMS LIST:

GA: Grant Agreement

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides in-depth information regarding D1.3: "Project Website", released in Month 6 (August 2018), from the RightsApp project. The project website is accessible through the link: <http://rightsapp-project.eu/>. Thus, this report shows the structure, content, design and usage statistics software used for the RightsApp project website.

Moreover, the two annexes also show the privacy and cookies policy and the legal notice contained within the website.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Deliverable D1.3 “Project website” releases the RightsApp project website. Additionally, this report contains specific details about the structure, content, design and visitors collected statistics.

Therefore, Section 2 of this report is focused on the different parts of the RightsApp project website: structure in Section 2.1; contents in Section 2.2; design in Section 2.3 that depicts different screenshots from the RightsApp website; and Section 2.4 shows the statistics collected by the project website. Finally, Section 3 summarizes all the contributions of this report and how the website will act as a tool for the project dissemination among the targeted users.

2 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project website is hosted at the UAB facilities and can be accessed through: <http://rightsapp-project.eu>.

2.1 Structure

Figure 1 shows the structure of the RightsApp website. The website structure is divided in five major parts: “Home”, “News”, “Events”, “Project structure” and “Dissemination”. “Project structure” and “Dissemination” have two additional subparts, which provide in-depth information: “Consortium” and “Deliverables”, and “Publications” and “Identity set”, respectively. Subparts are depicted in Figure 1 with fine dashed boxes. Moreover, at the bottom of each page appears a footer that contains: (i) the funding message and the website’s legal notice; (ii) the five most recent tweets from the RightsApp twitter account; (iii) the coordinator contact details; and (iv) the privacy and cookies policy that applies to the RightsApp website.

Figure 1: RightsApp project website structure.

2.2 Content

This Section explains the content of the website's parts introduced in Section 2.1 and Figure 1.

Home

The project website is the main online representation of the RightsApp project, thus the "Home" section, as a landing page, is intended to allow a quick overview on the project objectives, structure, stages of the project and the consortium members.

News

The "News" section highlights the news of the RightsApp project. It will show results, achievements, events attended or organized (conferences, workshops, tutorials, working meetings, among others), availability of public deliverables from the project and networking achievements. Additionally, this section also includes a search tool and the archive of past news.

Events

The "Events" section is mainly focused on the events organized by the RightsApp project. (workshops, working meetings, tutorials, infodays, among others).

Project structure

The "Project structure" section consists of two subsections which provide in-depth information about consortium and scheduled deliverables. The "Consortium" subsection contains the description of the consortium: the role of each member in the project, their logos and their expertise.

The "Deliverables" section shows one table for each Work Package planned in project. Every table includes: the scheduled deliverables (name and expected due date) and, if publicly available, a link to download the PDF document from the RightsApp Zenodo Community (see D1.1 "Data Management Plan" for further information about the RightsApp Zenodo Community).

Dissemination

The "Dissemination" section consists of two subsections which provide in-depth information about the publications and identity set elements related to the project. The "Publications" subsection contains all the publications generated by the consortium, including conference papers, journal articles, public deliverables, among others. At the moment of writing of this report, the "Publications" subsection only includes one public deliverable, during the course of the project this page will be continuously filled according to the results and achievements reached by the RightsApp project.

The "Identity set" subsection includes all the elements for the dissemination of the RightsApp project. At the moment of writing this report it contains the name, programme and funding information about the project and it also includes sections for the forthcoming poster and leaflet that will be delivered at Month 10 (December 2018). However, during the project this page will be continuously filled according to the dissemination needs of the RightsApp project.

Footer

The Footer section is included in all pages contained in the RightsApp website. It includes the funding message, following instructions from Article 22.1.2 on "Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem" in the GA. Additionally, the "Footer" section also includes the "Legal notice" (see Annex II) for the RightsApp website; the most recent tweets from the RightsApp twitter account; and the coordinator contact details. Finally, at the bottom of the section the "Privacy and cookies policy" information is displayed (see Annex I).

2.3 Design

This Section provides screenshots of the project website to show the design. Figure 2 shows the front page (“Home”). Figure 3 depicts the “News” page from the website. Figure 4 lists past, present and future events related with the RightsApp project. Figure 5 shows the section of the “Project structure”, that is the “Consortium” information at the top of the figure and the “Deliverables” section at the bottom of the figure that includes all the deliverables scheduled in the project and a link to download the public ones. The “Dissemination” page, depicted in Figure 6, is the last section and it has two parts: “Publications” at the top of the figure which contains all the public publications provided by the project (conferences, journals, software and deliverables); and “Identity set” at the bottom of the figure which provides all the information related to the dissemination regarding the project such as information about the funding, different versions of the logos; and the leaflet and the poster of the project (currently this is a work in progress).

Figure 2: Home section.

Figure 3: News section.

Figure 4: Events section

Figure 5: Project structure section. Top: Consortium. Bottom: Deliverables.

Figure 6: Dissemination section. Top: Publications. Bottom: Identity set.

2.4 Statistics

The generation of the anonymous statistics about the usage of the RightsApp project’s website will be performed by Google Analytics. Thus, the Google Analytics code to gather these anonymous statistics have been included in the project website. Figure 7 depicts the dashboard that includes the number of users and visits, when and where occur the most part of the visits, which device is the most common and which pages are the most visited. These anonymous statistics will help to tune up the website to maximize the dissemination to the targeted groups.

Figure 7: Statistics dashboard.

3 SUMMARY

This report shows the structure, content, design and collected statistics of the RightsApp project’s website, which is accessible through <http://rightsapp-project.eu>. The idea behind this website is to raise a dynamic tool, where researchers, experts, stakeholders and interested EU citizens can find relevant information about the project. Moreover, the website is also the main online representation of the RightsApp project, jointly with the social media channels that will be set up all along the project. At the moment of writing this report, only the Twitter channel is working. At a later stage, Facebook and LinkedIn

accounts will also be set up. In addition, the consortium will be continuously evaluating if other social media channels might also benefit the dissemination and promoting of the project.

Currently, the website consists of five sections: “Home”, “News”, “Events”, “Project structure” and “Dissemination”. These five sections have been described in the previous sections of this report. Additionally, subsections, design, legal notice, privacy and cookies policy and contact details have been also discussed.

ANNEX I – PRIVACY AND COOKIES POLICY

What are cookies?

A cookie is a small text file that a website saves on your computer or mobile device when you visit the site. It enables the website to remember your actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) over a period of time, so you don't have to keep re-entering them whenever you come back to the site or browse from one page to another.

How do we use cookies?

A number of our pages use cookies to remember:

- your display preferences, such as contrast colour settings or font size
- if you have agreed (or not) to our use of cookies on this site

Enabling these cookies is not strictly necessary for the website to work but it will provide you with a better browsing experience. You can delete or block these cookies, but if you do that some features of this site may not work as intended.

The cookie-related information is not used to identify you personally and the pattern data is fully under our control. These cookies are not used for any purpose other than those described here.

How to control cookies

All recent versions of popular browsers give you a level of control over cookies. You can set your browser to accept or reject all, or certain, cookies. For instructions on how to manage cookies, please read the 'Help' section of your browser or visit aboutcookies.org. Please be aware that some areas of our website may not function after you have changed your cookie settings. If you do this, however, you may have to manually adjust some preferences every time you visit the Site and some services and functionalities may not work.

ANNEX II – LEGAL NOTICE

Disclaimer

This website is the home page for the DG-Justice funded project “RightsApp: Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice” (hereinafter RightsApp), which has received funding from the DG-Justice European Union’s Programme (2014-2020) under Grant Agreement No. 785854.

The website falls under the responsibility of the RightsApp consortium. It is not concerned with commercial transactions or with the exchange of data for marketing purposes. Whereas we endeavour to keep the information up to date and correct, we make no representations or warranties of any kind, express or implied, about the completeness, accuracy, reliability, suitability or availability with respect to the website, or the information, products, services, or related graphics contained on the website for any purpose. The information in this website is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and liability.

It is our goal to minimize disruption caused by technical errors. However, some data or information on our site may have been created or structured in files or formats that are not error-free and we cannot guarantee that our service will not be interrupted or otherwise affected by such problems. The RightsApp consortium accepts no responsibility with regard to such problems incurred as a result of using this site or any linked external sites.

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Personal Data Protection

The RightsApp project is committed to users’ privacy. This website and all services provided through it are provided in accordance with [Regulation \(EC\) N° 45/2001](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2000, as well as the [Regulation \(EU\) 2016/679](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (General Data Protection Regulation).

Information Collection and Use

Although you can browse through this website without directly giving any information about yourself, in some cases, personal data could be indirectly processed through automated personal data collection via your browser. In this case, the personal data is limited to the following categories of information:

- cookies, as described [here](#)
- the type of web browser software you use
- the name of the domain from which you access the Internet
- the Internet address of the website from which you linked directly to the site
- the date and time you access the Site
- which pages you have visited on the Site

Such information will be used exclusively for the purposes of creating aggregate and anonymous statistics of user behaviour on our site (through Google Analytics), specifically with the objective of improving the site and ensuring its correct functioning; and to detect and address any abuses or security issues. Anyway,

personal data that is automatically collected will not be retained by us for more than a year after your most recent visit.

Users may directly contact RightsApp researchers via e-mail address: idt (at) uab (dot) cat. Storage and handling of such messages are subject to the data handling policy of the corresponding institution.

Third parties

Please note that our website contains links to third party sites and resources provided by third parties. Since we do not control them, we encourage you to review their privacy policies and to adhere to them. Such resources are provided without assurances (explicit or implied) of their lawfulness or fitness for your purposes. Note that you are responsible for complying with data protection law for any processing activities you undertake in relation to personal data obtained via this site.

Advertising

The RightsApp project website does not work with any third party that provides ads to this Site.